

Figure 1. Sample screens of the new NOIRLab website illustrating functionality on mobile to desktop platforms. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

New Website for NSF's NOIRLab

Mark Newhouse (NOIRLab)

When NSF announced the formation of the National Optical-Infrared Astronomy Research Laboratory on 1 October 2019, it was clear that the full name was quite a mouthful! A shorter name would be needed to make it easier to refer to, at the same time providing an option for a relatively short domain name for a website. At the time we used the interim name “OIR Lab” and set up an interim website at noirlab.edu to serve as our public website. When we received our official short name in the Northern Hemisphere spring of 2020, a targeted effort began to move NOIRLab’s public internet presence to its new domain at noirlab.edu. This public site has since been launched as the main web portal for the public and media to receive information about NSF-funded ground-based nighttime astronomy and the valuable data generated by NOIRLab facilities.

Each of NOIRLab’s five Programs—the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory, the Community Science and Data Center, the international Gemini Observatory, Kitt Peak National Observatory, and Rubin Operations—brings a long and rich history of scientific breakthroughs spanning more than five decades. The new website shines a spotlight on NOIRLab’s role as a focal point for community development of innovative scientific programs, the exchange of ideas, and creative development. NOIRLab’s infrastructure enables the astronomy community to advance humanity’s understanding of the Universe by exploring significant areas of astrophysics, including dark energy and dark matter, galaxies and quasars, the Milky Way, exoplanets, and small bodies in our own Solar System.

Features

The new website offers a complete archive of all NOIRLab information for the public and media—nearly 6,000 images with rich contextual metadata, hundreds of videos, news, print products, fulldome sequences for planetariums to download and show in their domes, and more.

Dive into the [full 3.2 gigapixels](#) of the first image from the Rubin Observatory LSST Camera. Subscribe to the latest [images](#) and [videos](#). Download the [whopping 124 GB sequence](#) of 8k planetarium frames that together show a 3-minute state-of-the-art timelapse sequence of a night at Gemini South. Read about each of the [more than 60 telescopes](#) operated or hosted by NOIRLab. Follow the progression of each of NOIRLab's programs through press releases back to 1994. All NOIRLab images and videos are directly available in the domes of more than 500 planetariums with a dynamic feed using a metadata standard called [Data2Dome](#).

The site is regularly updated with [press releases](#) and [announcements](#) from all of our Programs, as well as a [new image every week](#) featuring interesting and beautiful photographs of NOIRLab's facilities, as well as inspiring images taken by NOIRLab's many telescopes. Our diverse [education and engagement activities](#) are also highlighted on the site.

The assets are freely available to download and use under a [Creative Commons Attribution license](#). The site also offers a historical perspective, and archives of newsletters and announcements from the National Optical Astronomy Observatory (NOAO) and Gemini are available. The website can be accessed in both English and Spanish.

The system behind the site, Djangoplicity, is a tried and tested recipe used by ESA/Hubble, ESO, UNAWA, the IAU, the International Year of Astronomy 2009, and others. It is an open-source platform that integrates a standard Content

Management System for the web pages with Digital Asset Management of all the assets, as well as an automated system for delivery of content to different audiences. The system uses Django, which is a high-level Python web framework that encourages rapid development and clean, pragmatic design, and was designed to handle the pressing deadlines of a newsroom.

The Team Behind the Website

An effort like this does not happen overnight, or with just one or two people. The construction and delivery of the site was a heroic effort by several of NOIRLab's communication, education and IT staff, working with the company Enciso Systems. It is through their coordinated efforts that the new site has come to fruition.

- NOIRLab web project coordination: Mark Newhouse (NOIRLab)
- Development of noirlab.edu: Javier Enciso, Edison Arango, Edwin Moreno, Francisco Rodriguez and Andrés Linares (Enciso Systems)
- Content migration: Paula Velásquez, Ingrid Romero, Samuel Medina, Diego Palacios, Alejandro Vivas, Javier Riveros and Jonathan Garzón (Enciso Systems)
- Design: Jason Kalawe (NOIRLab), Peter Marenfeld (NOIRLab), Joy Pollard (NOIRLab), Emily Acosta (Vera C. Rubin Observatory)
- Infrastructure: Jason Kalawe (NOIRLab), Jared Eckersley (NOIRLab) & Enciso Systems
- Archive consolidation & post-processing: Mahdi Zamani & Maral Kosari
- Djangoplicity legacy development: Lars Holm Nielsen (ESO, ESA/Hubble & IAU), Mathias André (ESO, ESA/Hubble & IAU), Gurvan Bazin (ESO), and Bruno Rino (UNAWA)
- Djangoplicity project management: Lars Lindberg Christensen (NOIRLab)

